

Critical Infrastructure Protection in the Railway Sector

A 2030 Outlook

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1. Drivers of Critical Infrastructure Protection in the Railway Sector

Within the EU, the railway system along with the power grid are the most massive infrastructures due to their geographic coverage. Taken as a whole, the railway system belongs to the biggest human-made objects spanning the entire continent. Railways have played the key role on the continent since the industrial revolution and remain the pivotal element of the transportation infrastructure for commerce and passengers alike. Provided the infrastructure is developed adequately, rail plays a vital role in intermodal logistics, facilitating the efficient movement of containers between ports and inland hubs. This capability is essential for integrating various modes of transport, such as shipping, road, and rail, into a seamless supply chain. For example, the Port of Rotterdam, one of Europe's largest maritime hubs, heavily relies on its rail connections to transport goods to inland terminals across the EU, such as Duisburg in Germany and further to Linz in Austria. Similarly, in Italy, the Port of Trieste uses rail links to distribute goods, among others, throughout Central and Eastern Europe. By enabling these intermodal connections, rail supports strategic industries such as automotive and agriculture, as they depend heavily on relatively cheap transportation networks. For instance, Germany's automotive sector benefits from rail freight to transport vehicle components between factories and assembly plants, both domestically and across borders. Similarly, the agricultural industry in France utilizes rail to deliver grain and other products to major ports for international trade. The war in Ukraine has recently demonstrated that road transport is not a competitive alternative for agricultural mass products. In particular, Ukrainian agricultural products for export, mainly wheat and corn, were typically transported by rail and then by ships along maritime routes due to the sheer volume involved. Unfortunately, the Russian blockade of the main Black Sea ports and the damage to rail infrastructure forced the Ukrainians to rely more on road transport. This shift resulted in significant inefficiencies. A single freight train can transport up to 50,000 tons of grain, while a single truck can carry only about 25-30 tons. Consequently, replacing rail or maritime capacity with road transport requires thousands of extra trucks, leading to increased fuel costs, delays, and environmental impacts. As a result, the Ukrainian grain was not sufficiently competitive and they started to lose their traditional markets.

In 2022, the total of 398 billion tonne-kilometres for main undertaking were transported via rail in the EU [1]. In the relative terms, the rail sector accounts for approximately 17% of total inland freight transport in the EU [2]. Road transport dominates with the share of about 75%. This should be noted that while rail freight's market share has been relatively stable recently, it faces ongoing competition from the road transport due to infrastructure and efficiency challenges. As for passenger transport, rail accounts for 8% in terms of passenger-kilometers [3]. Overall, while the above numbers for rail

are significantly smaller than for road transport, it should be noted rail transport in the EU often carries a higher proportion of strategically important freight compared to road transport. This is particularly true for bulk goods, hazardous materials, and essential commodities like energy resources, minerals, and large-volume raw materials. Rail is well-suited for these types of freight due to its capacity for long-distance, heavy-load transport, reliability, and lower environmental impact.

The plans for further development of the rail sector: rail transport is one of the pillars of the European Green Deal. To this end, various EU initiatives are to make it increasingly convenient and sustainable. In particular, the regulations for the trans-European transport network (TEN-T) aim at enhancing rail connectivity and promoting rail as a greener travel alternative. According to these plans, rail services should become more efficient and attractive across the continent. Central to these efforts is the EU's Action Plan to significantly improve long-distance and cross-border passenger rail services. The target of this plan that launched in 2021 is to double high-speed rail traffic by 2030 and to triple it by 2050. The focus is on addressing barriers, enhancing interoperability, upgrading passenger rail infrastructure, and improving service quality across EU Member States. To further strengthen cross-border rail travel, the European Commission has endorsed 10 pilot projects designed to enhance cross-border rail services [4]. These projects include new routes and service upgrades across key rail cross-border corridors on the continent, for instance: Paris-Milan-Venice and Amsterdam-Barcelona, Hungary-Austria-Western Romania routes, and Amsterdam-London services.

Safety & Security: In terms of safety, European railways excel in the world [5]. Recently, there were years with no major accidents (causing five or more fatalities). Unfortunately, five major accidents occurred in 2022 and 2023. This includes the February 2023 collision at Tempi, Greece, which resulted in the loss of 57 lives. In 2022, in total there were 1 615 railway accidents in the EU, with a total of 808 persons killed and 593 seriously injured. This can be compared to India with nearly 21 thousand railway accident fatalities across the country that year [6]. The recent report [7] emphasizes that enhancing safety in the rail sector requires more than strict adherence to regulations; it necessitates cultivating a robust safety culture and a shared commitment within the sector to sustainable and secure operations throughout the Single European Railway Area (SERA). Moreover, it suggests that the adoption of a unified, EU-wide, safety reporting framework could address persistent challenges, particularly in areas where safety progress has plateaued, such as at level crossings and in protecting railway workers.

We start the discussion of the security issues by observing that a successful attack on railways could not only have a crippling impact on public safety and security, but it could also potentially trigger cascading effects that disrupt other critical European infrastructures. In this respect, unfortunately, railways are a natural high-value target of a potential attack due to the number of people and the nature and quantity of goods transported. As for people, rail systems, especially in urban and high-traffic corridors, often carry large numbers of passengers, making them vulnerable to attacks with high potential for casualties. Examples include commuter trains, metros, and high-speed rail, which are critical for mobility in densely populated regions. As for goods, rail's controlled environment and lower accident risk make it a preferred option for transporting hazardous materials in a safer way. This, however, introduces additional risk vector in terms of security. Sabotage targeting a transport of hazardous (e.g., highly flammable, explosive or radioactive) materials can have cascading effects not only on freight and passenger operations but also on the vast neighbourhood of the attack, potentially even undermining the habitability of a neighbourhood areas. These effects can be compounded during hybrid warfare scenarios, where state or non-state actors exploit such disruptions to weaken adversaries.

Given the increasing digitalization of railways, a lot of attention should be paid to the cybersecurity issues. In this respect, the European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA) published in 2021 an extensive report on railway cybersecurity focuses on identifying cyber risks within the rail sector, proposing frameworks and strategies for managing these risks, and offering recommendations of how to harmonize approaches across the EU. We will discuss some of the main findings of this report below.

We should also mention a few key European projects focused on enhancing railway safety and security:

1. **European GNSS Navigation Safety for Rail:** This project aims to improve train localization systems by integrating satellite navigation services like Galileo and EGNOS into the European Rail Traffic Management System (ERTMS). The ERTMS is a flagship initiative aimed at standardizing train control and signaling across Europe. It has two main components: (a) ETCS (European Train Control System): a standard for train signaling and speed control; and (b) GSM-R (Global System for Mobile Communications – Rail): a communication system for train operators. In a nutshell, the goal of the ERTMS is to ensure that trains can run seamlessly across borders without changing systems, enhancing safety and efficiency [8].
2. **SECRET Project:** SECurity of Railways against Electromagnetic aTtacks (SECRET) project focused on protecting rail systems from electromagnetic (EM) attacks, this project assessed potential threats to railway communication systems and developed protective solutions. These include robust communications architecture and an attack management system to mitigate risks such as jamming attacks [9].
3. **Europe's Rail Joint Undertaking:** it is the European partnership on rail research and innovation under the Horizon Europe programme (2020-2027). It is a successor of the Shift2Rail Joint Undertaking and it aims at providing technological and operational solutions to lead the transformation of the rail sector, including advancing digitalization and automation and creating modular and standardized solutions for easier cross-border integration.

It should be underlined that the above projects are part of broader initiatives under Horizon Europe and other EU frameworks to support sustainable and safe rail transport across Europe.

2. Challenges and Limitations

Some of the main challenges and limitation faced by railway operators in the scope of their physical and cyber-security are as follows:

- **Challenge 1 – Vulnerabilities Induced by Technological Complexity**

Railway systems comprise of extensive infrastructure, including (i) hardware: tracks, power lines, signaling systems, bridges, tunnels, stations, depots, trains and locomotives; and (2) software. A significant challenge lies in the coexistence of legacy and emerging technologies. Legacy systems—some of which may have been in use for many decades—are often incompatible with modern solutions (in particular, they are difficult to digitalize). On one hand, they may lack resilience against contemporary threats such as cyberattacks. On the other hand, they may be simple enough to be resilient to such attacks. Furthermore, while outdated components may still perform critical functions, they are typically more prone to failure. Unfortunately, emerging technologies like advanced signaling (e.g., the European Rail Traffic Management System, ERTMS), AI-based

analytics, and IoT devices introduce their own complexities, including risks of software vulnerabilities and interoperability issues.

The issues stemming from the technological complexity of railway systems, including the security dimension of these challenges, have been recognised for long by the EU authorities as one of the major challenges. Given this, there have been various efforts to integrate and technologically standardize the EU railway system and to remove technical barriers between national rail networks. These initiatives are driven by EU legislation, funding programs, and cooperation between Member States. Key efforts include:

- the introduction of the European Railway Traffic Management System (ERTMS), already briefly described above;
- Europe's Rail Joint Undertaking to support rail research and innovation (also see above);
- the EU has developed Technical Specifications for Interoperability (TSI) to ensure compatibility across key railway subsystems such as infrastructure, rolling stock, energy, and signaling. These specifications detail the requirements for technical and operational standards across the EU rail network;
- Fourth Railway Package - this legislative package from 2016 was meant to simplify and harmonize certification processes for rolling stock and railway operators, reducing administrative hurdles. It strengthened the European Union Agency for Railways (ERA) as the single certification authority for cross-border operations.

We also mention various funding and investment initiatives such as EU instrument "Connecting Europe Facility (CEF) – Mobility and Transport" that support projects to upgrade and expand rail infrastructure and to meet interoperability standards.

Nevertheless, despite these efforts, the challenges related to technological complexity of the EU railway system are by far not overcome.

- **Challenge 2 - Ease of Access & Sheer Size of the Rail Infrastructure vs. New Threats**

The extensive and open nature of rail networks creates numerous access points for potential attackers. Stations, tunnels, bridges, and unmanned rail crossings are difficult to monitor comprehensively, creating vulnerabilities. The situation here is similar to the road system or power grid. All these infrastructure systems are open to public by their very nature.

These vulnerabilities are amplified by the rapid emergence of new technological developments in AI, and robotics, accelerated by the Russian-Ukrainian war. Given the open nature and the sheer size of railways, these new technologies present a very significant challenge. For example, attackers may use unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) for:

- surveillance and intelligence gathering - UAVs equipped with cameras and sensors can be used by malicious actors to gather sensitive information about railway operations, infrastructure layouts, or vulnerabilities.
- physical sabotage – as the Russian-Ukrainian war demonstrated, UAVs are effective in delivering explosives to targets at very long distances. Given this, a technologically advanced attacker is now able to attack anywhere in the EU and anything, including key railway infrastructure components such as bridges, tunnels, or electrical substations.
- signal interference - UAVs can be also used to jam communication signals or interfere with train control systems, potentially causing delays or collisions.

It is important to underline that UAV technology became widely available. While long-range attacks (at targets hundreds of kilometers away) require military-grade equipment, shorter distance attacks may be performed using a drone for even a few hundred euro. Furthermore, it should be noted that, while a lot of attention is paid to UAVs, other types of unmanned vehicles (i.e. unmanned ground vehicles and unmanned underwater and surface vehicles) should be also considered a serious threat to the railway infrastructure. For instance, in Poland most rivers are under the supervision of a governmental institution Polish Waters which is a separate entity from the railway infrastructure operator that supervises the security of rail bridges (PKP PLK). As such, one can easily imagine an attack on a key rail bridge with the use of an unmanned underwater and surface vehicle.

- **Challenge 3 - Fragmentation of Security Resources**

The security forces responsible for protecting railways in the EU are diverse and vary by country due to differences in governance, legal frameworks, and railway ownership structures. In Germany the Federal Police (Bundespolizei) is responsible for railway security, including patrolling stations and responding to incidents on the rail network. In Italy, the Polizia Ferroviaria (Railway Police) is part of the Italian State Police. Similarly in Belgium. In other countries, like France and Poland, the force directly responsible for security of railways is a subsidiary of a national rail operator. Different arrangements in the EU countries may also involve a combination of public and private entities. Often private security services are used to supplement public forces. Such a division of responsibilities among national, regional, and private entities can complicate coordination. It should be mentioned that this challenge has been already identified by the EU authorities who have taken several steps toward addressing it. One key initiative to improve coordination and security in the railway sector is the creation of the EU Rail Passenger Security Platform [10], designed to facilitate information sharing and better coordination across Member States. This platform supports the exchange of information regarding security threats, which is vital for preventing unilateral national security measures that could disrupt cross-border rail services [11]. Nevertheless, it is far too little to address the fragmentation problem.

- **Challenge 4 - Third-Party Risks**

As many maintenance, construction, and operational tasks are outsourced (at levels that vary depending on a country), the third-party risks pose significant challenges to the security of railway infrastructure in the EU. In more detail:

- The physical infrastructure faces that type of risk from subcontractors. Also, rail networks rely heavily on electricity and other utilities, which are often managed by external providers. Furthermore, recently some major rail infrastructure projects rely on public-private partnerships (PPPs), e.g. Rail Baltica. While these arrangements result in financial and operational profits, they also introduce additional risks as private partners may prioritize profit over security measures.
- Furthermore, rail operators increasingly rely on third-party providers for IT systems, signaling technologies, and communications infrastructure.
- Next, due to the sheer size of the railway infrastructure, in many EU countries, third-party security firms are hired for support in surveillance, access control, and patrolling of stations and tracks. Unfortunately, this increases the risk of inadequate training, low standards, or insider threats from these providers.
- Third-party risks increase for cross-border rail operations because they involve multiple entities, including foreign rail operators, infrastructure managers, and security protocols.

- Freight rail operations typically involve numerous third parties, including shippers, cargo handlers, and warehouse operators. Risks include tampering with cargo or supply chain processes and theft or sabotage. As a matter of fact, this risk materialized recently in some European countries due to Russian-inspired attacks on couriers.

- **Challenge 5 - Still Insufficient Information Sharing and Collaboration**

Despite various efforts, information sharing and collaboration among railway operators in the EU remain limited, creating challenges for cross-border operations. Some key issues include fragmented data exchange systems and a lack of standardized ticketing platforms for passengers. With respect to this last issue, there is no unified European booking platform for cross-border rail journeys. While platforms like DB Navigator exist and they are a step in the good direction, still they do not integrate tickets from all operators, limiting consumer choices and accessibility.

The above list of challenges is not exhaustive, yet representative of some key security risks that must be addressed by railway operators.

3. Solution Guidelines: Towards new AI-backed CIP Capabilities and Resilience

To address the above-listed challenges there is need for developing, adopting and deploying novel CIP solutions for the critical infrastructures of the railway sector. The following solution guidelines, especially focused on inter-related AI-driven technologies, are envisaged:

- **Guideline 1 - Interoperability and Standardisation via Digitalisation:** Further efforts towards interoperability and standardisation should be increasingly focused on the application of recent technological advancements fuelled, to a large extent, by AI and increasing computational power [12]. One of such advancement is the Digital Twin (DT) technology that can be used to create virtual replicas of physical railway systems and then to simulate interactions between legacy and modern systems, identify potential failure points, and security issues, if coupled with IoT devices. An in-depth discussion of how this digital technology can be helpful can be found in Sarp *et al.* [13]. The authors argue that DT technology can be particularly useful in improving efficiency and helping to address some key sustainability challenges. This can be done by using the DT model for real-time monitoring and predictive analytics to optimize energy consumption, reduce emissions, and manage resources more effectively throughout the lifecycle of rail assets. Not only optimized routing, but also energy-efficient maintenance strategies can be simulated in the DT model. A well-developed DT model can be also used for Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) enabling informed decisions on design, materials, and operations, increasing safety. These benefits of the DT technology naturally extend to security issues [14]. In particular, a DT model can be used for real-time monitoring of the railway system and detecting any anomalies from IoT sensors and real-time data feed indicative of cyberattacks, equipment malfunctions, or physical intrusions. DT can also simulate potential cyberattacks on railway control systems, allowing operators to refine defenses against emerging threats, such as ransomware targeting signaling networks. We will discuss further the AI/IoT aspects in the next guideline.

- **Guideline 2 - The Deployment of AI and IoT Solutions for Perimetric Security:** AI and IoT solutions are well-suited to addressing the inherent vulnerabilities of railway systems, which are open by design and difficult to secure comprehensively. That is, there are many possible vectors of attack at many possible places, but effective security resources are severely limited given the challenge. The situation can be significantly improved with the widespread application of AI and IoT solutions for perimetric security augmenting the capabilities of human-based security. The main benefits can be summarised as follows:
 - These solutions excel over humans for perimeter security of large critical infrastructures like railways in specific scenarios due to their scalability, precision, and capacity to process vast amounts of data in real-time.
 - They are especially suited for monitoring large, sparsely populated areas, such as long stretches of track, where deploying human personnel is too costly and too impractical.
 - Importantly, these systems operate continuously without human fatigue and in a way that is unaffected by biases or emotional factors.
 - Another advantage is that AI systems are able to identify threats in real-time with speed and accuracy unmatched by humans.

Again, we should highlight the fact that perimetric AI-backed IoT technologies are indispensable to protect against a growing danger of hybrid attacks by both unsophisticated actors and state-backed actors who have access to advanced technological capabilities such as unmanned vehicles.¹

- **Guideline 3 – The Accelerated and Widespread Development of Unmanned Vehicle Technologies and Anti-Unmanned Vehicles Technologies:** as the Russian-Ukrainian war has demonstrated, the unmanned vehicle technology is the key direction of development in the modern warfare and it poses fundamental danger to critical infrastructure. It resulted in the unprecedented development of anti-drone technologies. They are, unfortunately, relatively expensive, and not widespread. The development of a much bigger production capacity of anti-drone systems is then a must. Interestingly, the war has also shown that unmanned vehicles are effective to fight off attacks by unmanned vehicles of the enemy. Given the size and geographical span of the railway system in the EU, and the imperfect performance of anti-drone systems, it will be impossible to provide effective security without developing unmanned vehicles that will be able of a rapid response to any imminent danger from an attack of this kind. Finally, we should mention that AI-backed drones can be used for many other purposes such as accessing areas that are unsafe or inaccessible to humans, such as beneath bridges or along high-altitude tracks.
- **Guideline 4 - The Widespread Deployment of AI Solutions for Threat Prediction and Resource Allocation:** The pan-European implementation of both previous guidelines (digitalisation, Digital Twin, IoT, and AI solutions) should play a transformative role as far as the challenge related to the fragmentation of railway security forces is concerned. Assuming standardized data collection process across the EU countries, AI technologies will enable proactive threat management across diverse entities responsible for railway security. In more detail, AI algorithms can analyse historical and real-time data from multiple countries, identifying trends, risks, and potential gaps in security coverage. This enables optimized and predictive resource allocation, reducing duplication of efforts and ensuring that the right assets are deployed to the right locations. At later stages, AI methods can be used to introduce elements of automation in the

¹ For a sample counter-drone AI-based solution see: <https://sentrycs.com/the-counter-drone-blog/the-evolution-of-ai-in-drones-implications-and-adaptations-for-counter-drone-technology/>

coordination of cross-border responses by using pre-defined protocols for communication and task delegation among different countries' forces. This will reduce delays caused by bureaucratic processes. We note that the EU Rail Passenger Security Platform already supports some level of information exchange. However, integrating advanced digital tools, such as AI-powered threat detection and secure communication channels, would enhance its effectiveness. Furthermore, AI coupled with Digital Twin models can be used as virtual training platforms to simulate cross-border threat scenarios, enabling training personnel from different countries to work cohesively. Perhaps the best example of activities in such a direction in the EU can be found in the cyberspace.²

- **Guideline 5 – The Development and Deployment of EU AI Tool to Due Diligence:** Given the resource constrained, the third-party risks outlined above cannot be challenged by other means than AI tools for due diligence. There are various solutions available on the market already³, but we advocate the development of EU tool for this task. It would also be crucial to consider the requirements on supply chain value assessments introduced by the NIS 2 Directive, as these directly influence the standards and compliance measures expected from third-party risk management processes.

4. The role of the EU-CIP project

EU-CIP is pivotal in enhancing the security, resilience, and innovation of critical infrastructure. Its mission encompasses bolstering Europe's analytical capabilities, maximizing the impact of research and innovation (R&I) efforts, and fostering a robust ecosystem that connects and empowers stakeholders across the EU. To support the implementation of the outlined guidelines and recommendations, EU-CIP's coordination and support activities offer valuable assistance.

1. Enhancing Europe's Analytical Capabilities (EU-CIP-ANALYSIS)

- **Addressing New Threats:** The railway sector whitepaper emphasizes the emergence of new threats, particularly related to the unmanned vehicle technology backed by AI. EU-CIP's structured approach to collecting and analysing information about resilient infrastructures can provide crucial insights and foresight into the level of readiness against these new evolving threats, enabling the railway sector to anticipate and prepare for future challenges more effectively.
- **Advocating Digitalisation, Robotisation and AI Development and Deployment:** The whitepaper highlights that the vulnerabilities of the EU railway system as a whole will not be addressed without a coherent and thorough digitalisation of the infrastructure and the widespread application of Robotics and AI. EU-CIP's analytical capabilities, including its observatory of CIP/CIR research outcomes, technologies, policies, and standards, can provide valuable intelligence and best practices to enhance the protection of these critical railway infrastructures via these new technologies.

²In 2021, a Joint Cyber Unit was created. The body was tasked with coordinating a joint response to large-scale cyberattacks hitting EU member states (<https://therecord.media/eu-announces-joint-cyber-unit-to-respond-to-large-scale-security-incidents>).

³ See, for example, <https://www.leewayhertz.com/ai-in-due-diligence/>.

2. Amplifying the Impact of R&I CIP/CIR Activities (EU-CIP-AMPLIFY)

- **The Development of the Digital Twins of the Railways in the EU:** As the whitepaper notes both the complexity of the railway infrastructure as well as expanding array of threats are growing. An important step to deal with this challenge is the development of Digital Twins of the railway infrastructure in the EU. EU-CIP's Amplify pillar offers tailored innovation services, including guidance on addressing gaps in existing solutions, fostering alignment with EU standards, and facilitating stakeholder collaboration through co-creation activities. These efforts ensure that Digital Twin technologies are not only innovative but also practical, resilient, and ready for adoption across the European railway sector.
- **Validating and Commercializing Digital Innovations:** EU-CIP provides a virtualized testbed for experimenting with standards-based CIP/CIR solutions and certification schemes, which is particularly relevant for the IT sector, due to high complexity of IT solutions that need to be validated before deployment.

3. Establishing a Vibrant Ecosystem (EU-CIP-ECOSYSTEM)

- **Promoting Cooperation in the Railway Sector:** The whitepaper emphasizes that stakeholders of the railway sector must work together to deal with the challenges, especially those of transnational nature. This requirement is fulfilled through EU-CIP's objective of establishing a Knowledge Hub and building a community around its analytical and innovation support services. This initiative promotes knowledge sharing, collaboration, and a unified approach to tackling the challenges confronting the railway sector.
- **Participation in Standard and Policy Development:** The whitepaper emphasizes the value of the unification of international railway security practices and technology. EU-CIP's ecosystem approach, combined with its proactive dissemination and communication strategy, ensures that the needs and challenges of the railway industry are effectively represented and supported in policy development and standardization efforts by encouraging the active involvement of relevant stakeholders.

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